

1 **Influence of genetic and interannual factors in the phenolic profiles of virgin**
2 **olive oils**

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20 **Abstract**

21 Phenolic compounds in virgin olive oil (VOO) contribute to its health properties, organoleptic
22 features and oxidative stability. In this study, a total of 44 olive tree cultivars categorized by the
23 International Olive Council to be among the most internationally widespread varieties were
24 exhaustively and homogenously evaluated by analysis of the VOO phenolic profile during three
25 consecutive crop seasons. Differences among cultivars resulted in up to 15-fold variations in the total
26 phenol concentration. The ‘cultivar’ factor contributed the most to the variance (66.8% for total
27 phenolic concentration) for almost all the phenols. However, the ‘interannual variability’ factor and
28 the interaction ‘cultivar × interannual variability’ exhibited significant influences on specific phenols.
29 According to the phenolic profile of the VOOs, we determined the presence of three groups of
30 cultivars marked by the predominance of secoiridoid derivatives, which supports the phenolic profile
31 as a criterion to be considered in olive breeding programs.

32

33 **Keywords:** *Olea europaea*; phenols; crop season; cultivar; genotype; virgin olive oil; clustering;
34 classification.

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36 ***Chemical compounds studied in this article***

37 Hydroxytyrosol (PubChem CID: 82755); Oleacein (3,4-DHPEA-EDA) (PubChem CID: 18684078);
38 Oleocanthal (p-HPEA-EDA) (PubChem CID: 16681728); Oleuropein aglycone (3,4-DHPEA-EA)
39 (PubChem CID: 124202093); Ligstroside Aglycone (p-HPEA-EA) (PubChem CID: 11652416);
40 Luteolin (PubChem CID: 5280445); Apigenin (PubChem CID: 5280443).

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43 1. Introduction

44 Olive tree (*Olea europaea* L.) is characterized by a vast number of cultivars that represent an
45 invaluable heritage of genetic variability selected over more than 5500 years of cultivation in
46 Mediterranean countries ¹. Based on the FAO Olive Germplasm Plant Production and Protection
47 Division data, the world olive germplasm comprises over 2.600 different olive cultivars ².

48 Virgin olive oil (VOO), the most valuable product obtained from the olive tree, is one of the
49 supporting pillars of the health properties associated with the Mediterranean diet, which considerably
50 contributes to the prevention of chronic diseases ³⁻⁵. Chemically, VOO is composed of major
51 components (approximately 98% of the total weight), mainly fatty acids such as acylglycerides, and
52 minor components (2%) that include a diversity of chemical families such as aliphatic and triterpenic
53 alcohols, sterols, hydrocarbons, phenols, tocopherols, esters, pigments and volatile components ⁶. The
54 high presence of monounsaturated oleic acid (55–83%) is one of the main contributors to the health
55 benefits of olive oil ⁷. The phenolic fraction also contributes significantly to these benefits due to its
56 antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties ^{5,8-10}. For instance, the phenolic
57 compound oleocanthal has demonstrated activity in reducing inflammatory-related diseases and
58 specific cancers ¹¹, acting through similar mechanisms to that of the nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory
59 drug (NSAID) ibuprofen ¹². Additionally, the same study suggested that the long-term consumption
60 of 50 g of extra-VOO (containing 200 mg/kg oleocanthal) per day corresponded to approximately
61 10% of the ibuprofen dosage recommendation for adult pain relief ¹². In 2011, the European Food
62 Safety Authority (EFSA) approved the claim: “olive oil phenols contribute to the protection of blood
63 lipids from oxidative stress”. This claim may be added to a product label when the VOO contains at
64 least 5 mg of hydroxytyrosol and its derivatives (e.g., oleuropein complex and tyrosol) per 20 g of
65 olive oil ⁴.

66 Phenolic compounds also contribute to the organoleptic properties of VOO. They stimulate
67 the tasting receptors in the mouth and free endings of trigeminal nerves, eliciting bitterness, pungency
68 and astringency perception ^{6,13,14}. Additionally, phenols protect VOO against oxidation because they

69 scavenge free radicals, which provoke the oxidative chain reaction and dramatically reduce the
70 quality of olive oil ¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

71 In VOO, different groups of phenolic compounds, such as phenolic acids, phenolic alcohols,
72 hydroxy-isochromans, flavonoids, lignans, and secoiridoids, are found. However, secoiridoids, such
73 as the aldehydic forms of oleuropein and ligstroside aglycone, oleocanthal and oleacein, are the
74 predominant phenolic compounds of VOO. These compounds are also the most important regarding
75 health properties, oil oxidative stability and organoleptic contribution ¹⁸⁻²⁰.

76 Genotype (cultivar) significantly contributes to the composition and concentration of most
77 important phenols found in VOO when agronomic conditions are controlled ^{21,22}. However,
78 differential climatic variables such as water availability or annual temperatures, rainfall, light
79 exposure, and fertilization also play important roles in the phenolic variability in VOOs ^{23,24}. For
80 instance, an increase in water availability involves a reduction in the total phenolic concentration in
81 fresh olive fruit and in the extracted oil ^{25,26}. Likewise, dry summers and autumns seem to increase
82 the phenolic content ²³. Additionally, olive fruits in shaded areas of the canopy have higher phenolic
83 contents than those of fruits in well-illuminated zones ²⁷. However, these studies present several
84 limitations, such as the scarce number of cultivars evaluated and the absence of interannual crop
85 replicates.

86 The effect of interannual variation has been evaluated in other relevant VOO fractions, such
87 as fatty acids. Several studies have concluded that the relative influence of climatic and environmental
88 conditions on fatty acid composition is relatively low, with cultivar being the most relevant factor
89 impacting variability in the fatty acid profile ²⁸⁻³⁰. This result has allowed for the selection of new
90 olive cultivars with specific fatty acid profiles considering only a single year of evaluation ³⁰.

91 To our knowledge, there are no studies evaluating the relative effect of the cultivar and
92 interannual variability sources on the VOO phenolic profile in a representative number of cultivars.
93 Estimating this phenolic variation is crucial to assess a) the interannual consistency of the attributes
94 related to VOO quality, such as health benefits and organoleptic properties; b) the effect of specific

95 interannual variables, such as climatic factors, average temperature or pluviometry, on VOO phenolic
96 profiles; c) the possible specific interactions between cultivar and interannual variables; and d)
97 possible new breeding lines to obtain new cultivars enriched in specific phenolic compounds. In this
98 respect, it is necessary to estimate the minimum number of necessary years to perform a consistent
99 evaluation of phenolic compounds, taking into account their interannual variability, which will
100 depend not only on the heritability but also on the stability of the phenolic composition. In this study,
101 we focused on evaluating the phenolic profiles of 44 olive cultivars growing under the same
102 conditions during three consecutive crop seasons. The selected cultivars covered the remarkable
103 genetic diversity and heterozygosity of traditional olives ^{31,32}.

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105 **2. Material and methods**

106 **2.1. Experimental location and vegetal material**

107 Vegetal material was collected from the World Olive Germplasm Bank of Cordoba (WOGB) (CAP-
108 UCO-IFAPA), specifically in the collection located at the University of Cordoba (Cordoba, Spain,
109 37°55'56.5" N, 4°43'13.3" W and 173 m a.s.l.). The olives were planted in 2011 in a north-south
110 orientation with 7 m between rows and 6 m between trees (238 trees ha⁻¹). This collection includes
111 368 different cultivars from 22 different countries that were correctly identified and authenticated by
112 morphological and DNA molecular markers ³².

113 The climate of the WOGB-UCO area is typically Mediterranean; the average annual
114 precipitation and potential evapotranspiration from 2001 to 2017 were 549.5 and 1317.6 mm,
115 respectively. The accumulated rainfall in 2015, 2016 and 2017 was 352.1, 735.8, and 463.5 mm,
116 respectively ³³. The experimental area is characterized by vertisol soil with a texture of 41% sand, 6%
117 silt, and 53% clay. The soil was approximately 40 cm deep, with a 0.6% organic matter content. The
118 collection was irrigated from May to September, applying 100 m³ of water per ha per week (2000 m³
119 of water per year) using drip irrigation. Foliar fertilization (2% potassium nitrate) was applied four
120 times per year in November (after harvesting), March, May, and September.

121 During three consecutive crop seasons (2015/16, 2016/17, and 2017/18), we extracted and
122 analyzed the VOOs of 44 olive cultivars. These cultivars were selected according to their share of
123 olive oil production worldwide, geographical origin, and genetic diversity (**Table 1**). Two fruit
124 samples per cultivar were independently collected from two olives. Therefore, we analyzed a total of
125 264 samples of VOO during three consecutive years (44 cultivars \times 2 replicates \times 3 crop seasons =
126 264 samples).

127

128 **2.2. Sampling and VOO extraction**

129 Olive fruit samples (2 kg) were manually harvested from each tree by sampling all orientations within
130 the canopy. The olives were sampled from October to December when the fruits were at a ripening
131 index (RI) of 2.0 (yellowish-red color) according to the method proposed by the International Olive
132 Oil Council ³⁴.

133 The extraction of VOOs was conducted by an Abencor system (MC2 Ingeniería y Sistemas,
134 Sevilla, Spain) under optimized conditions ³⁵. The olive fruits were crushed with a hammer mill
135 equipped with a 4-mm sieve at 3000 rpm. Malaxation of olive pomace was performed at 28 °C for 30
136 min; then, the biphasic system was centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 2 min. No water was added to the
137 olive pomace at any step of the process. The VOO was decanted in graduated cylinders for
138 approximately 2 h. Water traces were removed by filtering the samples through a cellulose filter. The
139 samples were stored in amber glass bottles at -20 °C until analysis.

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141 **2.3. Reagents and standards**

142 Mass spectrometry (MS)-grade methanol (MeOH) and *n*-hexane, both from Scharlab (Barcelona,
143 Spain), were used for the determination and quantification of the phenolic compounds in the VOOs.
144 MS-grade formic acid, also from Scharlab, was used as an ionization agent in the chromatographic
145 mobile phases. Deionized water (18 M Ω •cm) from a Millipore Milli-Q water purification system

146 (Bedford, MA, USA) was used to prepare both the aqueous and organic mobile phases, and a
147 hydroalcoholic mixture was used as the sample extractant.

148 The quantified phenolic compounds were hydroxytyrosol, oleacein (3,4-DHPEA-EDA),
149 oleocanthal (p-HPEA-EDA), oleuropein aglycone (3,4-DHPEA-EA), ligstroside aglycone (p-HPEA-
150 EA), luteolin, and apigenin. Two isomers of oleuropein and ligstroside aglycones were distinguished
151 according to their retention times³⁶. Thus, it was possible to discriminate between the open aldehyde
152 form of oleuropein aglycone (AOleAgly) and the closed monoaldehyde form of the oleuropein
153 aglycone (MAOleAgly). In the same way, it was possible to differentiate among the open aldehyde
154 form of ligstroside aglycone (ALigAgly) and the closed monoaldehyde form of ligstroside aglycone
155 (MALigAgly). Standards for hydroxytyrosol, apigenin and luteolin were purchased from
156 Extrasynthese (Genay, France). Oleacein, oleocanthal, and the closed monoaldehyde isomers of
157 oleuropein aglycone and ligstroside aglycone were provided by Professor Prokopios Magiatis
158 (University of Athens, Greece). The open aldehyde forms were quantified using the corresponding
159 closed monoaldehyde standards. Standard solutions of nonsecoiridoid phenols were prepared in
160 methanol (1 mg/mL), while secoiridoids were prepared at the same concentration in pure acetonitrile
161 to preserve their stability and avoid undesired conversion to their acetal and hemiacetal derivatives.

162

163 **2.4. Sample preparation for analysis of phenolic compounds**

164 We implemented a liquid-liquid extraction method for the isolation of phenols according to a previous
165 protocol³⁷. For this purpose, 1 g of VOO was mixed with 2 mL *n*-hexane; then, 1 mL of 60:40 (v/v)
166 methanol-water was added and shaken for 2 min, and the hydroalcoholic phase was separated by
167 centrifugation. The extraction was repeated to enhance the extraction efficiency³⁶, and the two
168 resulting extracts were combined for each sample. The extracts were analyzed by LC-QqQ-MS/MS
169 with two different dilution factors (1:2 and 1:50 v/v) to encompass the concentration variability.

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171 2.5. LC–MS/MS analysis of phenolic compounds

172 Analyses were performed by reversed-phase liquid chromatography followed by electrospray
173 ionization (ESI) in negative mode with tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) detection. Ten
174 microliters of the extract was injected in triplicate into the LC system for chromatographic separation
175 of the target compounds using a C18 Pursuit XRs Ultra column (50 mm×2.0 mm i.d., 2.8 µm particle
176 size) from Varian (Walnut Creek, CA, USA). The column compartment was kept at 30 °C. Mobile
177 phase A was 0.1% (v/v) formic acid in water, while phase B was 0.1% (v/v) formic acid in MeOH.
178 The gradient program, at a constant flow rate of 0.4 mL/min, was as follows: initially, 50% phase A
179 and 50% phase B were maintained for 0.5 min; from 0.5 to 2 min, mobile phase A decreased from 50
180 to 20%; and from min 2 to 4, mobile phase A decreased from 20 to 0%. This last composition was
181 maintained for 1 min. After each analysis, the column was equilibrated for 5 min at the initial
182 conditions.

183 The entire eluate was ionized via electrospray ionization and monitored by MS/MS in multiple
184 reaction monitoring (MRM) mode for selective transitions from the most favored precursor ion to
185 product ion of each analyte. The MRM parameters for the target phenols are listed in **Supplementary**
186 **Table 1**. The flow rate and temperature of the drying gas (N₂) were 10 L/min and 300 °C, respectively.
187 The nebulizer pressure was 50 psi, and the capillary voltage was 3000 V. The dwell time was set at
188 200 µs.

189 190 2.6. Quantitation of the target compounds and statistical analysis

191 Calibration curves were prepared by using refined sunflower oil spiked with variable concentrations
192 of the phenolic standards (nine concentrations from 0.1 ng/mL to 5 µg/mL). Each concentration level,
193 prepared in triplicate, was analyzed after the complete procedure including sample preparation. The
194 absence of quantifiable levels of phenols in the refined oil was checked by direct analysis. The
195 calibration equations were used to calculate the absolute concentration of target phenols in the VOO

196 samples and the “Sum of phenols” parameter by the addition of the individual concentrations of the
197 different phenols. Three replicates of each VOO were also analyzed to obtain the mean concentration.

198 Friedman nonparametric two-way analysis of variance was performed to evaluate the effect
199 of the cultivar on the concentrations of the nine phenolic compounds. This test was used because the
200 data did not satisfy the requirements of parametric tests regarding normality, homogeneity of
201 variance, or sphericity. The means were compared using Dunn’s test with a Bonferroni adjustment (p
202 = 0.05) ³⁸.

203 To estimate the stability of the VOO phenolic composition for each cultivar during the three
204 studied periods, we calculated the proportion of variability explained by the cultivar, interannual
205 variability sources, and the cultivar × interannual variability interaction. For this purpose, analysis of
206 variance (ANOVA) was performed on the phenolic composition of VOOs produced by the cultivars
207 during the three consecutive crop seasons with a representative number of repetitions (two olive trees
208 of the same cultivar). Subsequently, we calculated the effect size (eta squared [η^2]) of each
209 independent variable (cultivar and season) and its interaction as the ratio between the variability
210 associated with a factor and the total variability of our analysis ($\eta^2 = \frac{SS_{factor}}{SS_{total}}$). Friedman and
211 ANOVA tests were performed using 269 Statistix software (Version 10; Statistix, Tallahassee, FL).

212 Furthermore, principal component analysis (PCA) followed by discriminant analysis (DA)
213 was used to identify groups of cultivars with similar phenolic profiles. The existence of significant
214 pairwise differences between the groups depicted by PCA was evaluated with a Bonferroni post hoc
215 test, while Pearson correlation was used to find relationships between the concentrations of studied
216 phenols. These analyses were performed using XLSTAT software (v.2014.5.03, Addinsoft, Paris,
217 France).

218

219 3. Results and discussion

220 3.1. Variability in the phenolic profile of VOOs

221 We measured the individual concentrations of nine phenolic compounds and the “Sum of phenols”
222 in the VOOs of 44 olive cultivars during three consecutive crop seasons. The mean values of phenolic
223 concentrations are presented in **Table 1**. Similar to previous studies ^{29,39,40}, we found significant
224 differences ($p < 0.05$) in phenolic content among cultivars. For instance, the total phenolic content
225 (“Sum of phenols”) was 9-fold higher in VOO from the ‘Cerezuela’ cultivar than in that from the
226 ‘Royal de Cazorla’ cultivar (3208 *versus* 290 mg/kg, respectively).

227 In agreement with previous studies ^{41,42}, the frequency distributions of cultivars according to
228 their phenolic concentration were nonsymmetric (**Figure 1**), and almost all phenols reported right
229 skew parameters explaining the predominance of cultivars with relatively low contents of these
230 compounds. Homogeneous cultivar groups according to the concentration of the nine phenolic
231 compounds were identified by the Friedman test (**Table 1**). However, we determined the best
232 cultivars according to the total and average concentrations of each phenol. Regarding the Sum of
233 phenols, ‘Cerezuela’, ‘Cornicabra’, and ‘Plementa Bjelica’ samples reported maximum phenolic
234 contents of 3208, 2923, and 2841 mg/kg, respectively. The richest cultivars in oleocanthal were
235 ‘Kalamon’, ‘Plementa Bjelica’ and ‘Alfafara’, with 1186, 936 and 852 mg/kg, respectively, while
236 ‘Cerezuela’, ‘Mision Moojeski’ and ‘Kalamon’ were the richest in oleacein, containing 1333, 904
237 and 875 mg/kg, respectively,. Complementarily, the cultivars that stood out in concentration of
238 oleuropein aglycone isomers were ‘Chetoui’, ‘Coratina’ and ‘Cornicabra’, with 1170, 1065 and 933
239 mg/kg, respectively, and, for ligstroside aglycone isomers, these were ‘Cornicabra’, ‘Frantoio’ and
240 ‘Manzanilla Prieta’ with 925, 801 and 753 mg/kg, respectively.

241 The most abundant individual phenols (mean values) found in this three-year study were the
242 oleuropein aglycone isomers (447 mg/kg), oleacein (407 mg/kg), oleocanthal (319 mg/kg) and
243 ligstroside aglycone isomers (292 mg/kg) (**Table 2**). These results are in qualitative and quantitative
244 concordance with experimental results previously reported by other authors ^{22,29,39,42}.

246 3.2. Factors contributing to VOO phenolic variability

247 The phenolic profile of VOOs is affected by several factors, such as the cultivar (genotype), fruit
248 phenological stage (ripening), alternate bearing, location and climatic conditions, and agronomic
249 practices^{39,43,44}. However, the magnitude and relative influence of these factors on the chemical
250 composition of VOO and, specifically, in the present phenols, have been poorly explored. In this
251 study, we evaluated for the first time the effect of the cultivar and the interannual variation as well as
252 the interaction between both factors on VOO phenolic variability. The rest of the mentioned factors
253 hardly affected our results because the evaluated cultivars were the same age, in the same orchard
254 and under the same agronomic management; thus, we considered them fixed factors.

255 Variation in the average concentration of the nine evaluated phenolic compounds during the
256 three consecutive agronomic seasons is summarized in **Table 2**. We observed some compounds with
257 high between-year variability; for example, oleacein exhibited mean levels of 276 and 225 mg/kg in
258 the first two seasons, while in the third season, its concentration increased up to 721 mg/kg. On the
259 other hand, the concentrations of aglycone isomers of oleuropein and ligstroside were relatively stable
260 over time (**Table 2**).

261 ANOVA confirmed that the cultivar, the interannual variation and the interaction between
262 both factors (cultivar \times interannual variation) significantly ($p < 0.001$) affected the concentration of
263 VOO phenols (**Table 3**). According to the eta squared (η^2) value, the cultivar was the principal factor
264 explaining up to 66.8% of the total phenolic (Sum of phenols) variability. The interannual variation
265 explained just 3.7% of the variability, while the cultivar \times interannual variation interaction accounted
266 for 24.5% of the total variance. Similarly, the cultivar was the factor impacting the concentration of
267 individual phenols the most. However, not all individual phenols were equally affected by cultivar.
268 **Figure 2** shows that oleocanthal and aglycone isomers of oleuropein and ligstroside were mainly
269 influenced by the cultivar factor, with over 50% of the total variability explained by the cultivar

270 (above 60% for oleocanthal and AOleAgly). Furthermore, the cultivar was the secondary factor in
271 explaining the variability of oleacein, hydroxytyrosol and the two flavonoids apigenin and luteolin.
272 Our results are in agreement with those of previous studies that evaluated the phenolic variability in
273 olives and other crop species, highlighting the high impact of the genotype on phenolic profiles^{39,45,46}.
274 Therefore, the genotype is the most relevant factor in the breeding of new olive cultivars providing
275 high phenolic VOOs. Similarly, according to previous studies, the genetic factor is the most relevant
276 in defining the fatty acid profile of VOOs, contributing between 40 and 90% of the total fatty acid
277 variance^{6,47}.

278 Climatic variables, such as accumulated rainfall, temperature variation, and light interception,
279 are the key factors that affect the phenolic content of olive fruits during oil accumulation, normally
280 from July (pit hardening) to November, which corresponds with fruit harvesting^{23,24,27,48–50}. Given
281 the restricted number of seasons monitored in this research, it was not possible to establish any strong
282 relationship between these variables and the annual variability that we observed in the VOO phenolic
283 profile. However, we observed some general trends regarding precipitation values and the overall
284 phenolic concentration of the VOOs that were in line with those of previous studies^{23,48–51}. We
285 observed that the year with the lowest accumulated rainfall during the oil accumulation period (2017)
286 produced fruits with the highest phenolic contents (**Supplementary Figure 1**). On the other hand, no
287 remarkable relationship was observed between the mean temperatures and the mean phenolic
288 concentrations of VOOs. This fact may be explained by the lack of significant differences among the
289 mean temperatures in the analyzed crop seasons (**Supplementary Figure 1**).

291 **3.3. Clustering of olive cultivars based on the VOO phenolic profile**

292 A previous study based on data from one agronomic season²², defined four tentative groups of
293 cultivars according to their VOO phenolic profiles: (i) oils rich in aglycone isomers of oleuropein and
294 ligstroside, (ii) oils rich in oleocanthal and oleacein, (iii) oils rich in flavonoids, and (iv) oils with
295 balanced but reduced phenolic concentrations. The present research extended this evaluation during

296 three consecutive agronomic seasons to evaluate interannual variability effects, mainly due to
297 climatological variables. For this purpose, PCA based on the average phenolic concentrations in
298 VOOs obtained from three agronomic seasons was carried out to determine clusters of cultivars based
299 on their phenolic profiles. **Figure 3** shows the PCA biplot with the two principal components (PC1
300 and PC2) explaining 63.7% of the total variability. The 44 cultivars were grouped into three groups,
301 especially conditioned by predominantly containing the aglycone isomers of oleuropein and
302 ligstroside; *G2* (13 cultivars), enriched with oleocanthal and oleacein compounds; and *G3* (12
303 cultivars), with balanced and no remarkable content of any specific phenol (**Supplementary Table**
304 **2**). In general, this classification agreed with the results proposed by Miho *et al.* in one agronomic
305 season²². The only difference was that a fourth group of cultivars leading to VOOs with high
306 concentrations of flavonoids was not identified in the extended three-season research probably
307 because the concentration of flavonoids was not stable enough over time in this group, which was
308 formed by only 10 cultivars.

309 ANOVA with a Bonferroni post hoc test was performed to find statistically significant
310 differences in phenolic concentrations among these three groups of cultivars defined by PCA. The
311 results supported this classification since *G1* and *G2* cultivars were characterized by VOOs
312 significantly rich ($p < 0.0001$) in the aglycone isomers of oleuropein and ligstroside and the sum of
313 oleocanthal and oleacein, respectively (**Figure 4**). In contrast, the *G3* group included VOOs that
314 reported a low phenolic content without significant differences ($p > 0.05$) between the concentration
315 of aglycone isomers of oleuropein and ligstroside and the sum of oleocanthal and oleacein. The *G1*
316 group exhibited a mean concentration of aglycone isomers of oleuropein and ligstroside of 1166
317 mg/kg, and the *G2* group exhibited a corresponding concentration of 536 mg/kg. On the other hand,
318 the *G2* group provided a mean concentration of oleocanthal + oleacein of 1275 mg/kg *versus* 491
319 mg/kg for the *G1* group. The *G3* group provided mean concentrations of 318 and 362 mg/kg for
320 aglycone isomers and oleocanthal + oleacein, respectively. These results highlight the relevance of
321 the secoiridoid derivatives for the classification of olive cultivars. These secoiridoids are produced

322 by enzymatic action from the precursors oleuropein and ligstroside. The aglycone isomers of
323 oleuropein and ligstroside are produced by β -glucosidases through hydrolysis, whereas oleocanthal
324 and oleacein are formed by the combined action of β -glucosidases and methylesterases^{14,52}. Thus,
325 the enzymatic conversion of oleuropein and ligstroside precursors is a phenotypic characteristic that
326 can be measured by determining the concentration of secoiridoids in VOO.

327 To confirm that the olive cultivars were correctly classified by PCA, discriminant analysis
328 (DA) considering the total olive sample replications was carried out (**Supplementary Figure 2**).
329 Likewise, DA corroborated that the phenolic profiles of most cultivars did not change with increasing
330 crop year. In particular, 85.2% of cultivars were classified during three consecutive seasons in the
331 same PCA group, whereas only 14.8% changed their group assignment over the seasons
332 (**Supplementary Table 3**). Most likely, these last cultivars presented increased sensitivity to
333 interannual factor variability, or levels of certain phenols were relatively close to the threshold for
334 classification into the G3 group. Indeed, cultivar allocation changes occurred from *G1* and *G2* groups
335 to G3 or *vice versa*, but no changes were observed between *G1* and *G2*. This result indicates that the
336 *G3* cultivar group may be considered an intermediate group, while *G1* and *G2* groups include
337 cultivars providing VOOs with contrasting and relatively stable phenolic profiles.

338 Our results highlight for the first time the relative stability of the VOO phenolic profile over
339 several cultivation years in an extended set of olive cultivars. This main finding, along with previous
340 breeding experiences in other fruit species such as blueberry, raspberry, and peach^{53,54 53,54}, indicates
341 the possibility of developing health-enhanced olive cultivars able to produce VOOs enriched in
342 specific phenols. The selection of olive cultivars to be used as progenitors in a breeding program and
343 the estimation of their genetic contribution to the biotransformation of phenols are imperative¹.
344 Consumers are increasingly willing to pay for food quality, especially for healthy fruits and
345 vegetables^{46,55,56}. Given that olive breeding is a lengthy process, breeders of perennial species should
346 expect future market trends at least 10 years ahead⁵⁷. This study opens new venues to obtaining
347 healthy olive cultivars to satisfy consumer requirements.

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388 **Funding Sources**

389 This research was jointly financed by the Interreg-Med Program through the project MED-1033 and
390 the European Regional Development Fund/European Social Fund (“Investing in your future”). H.
391 Miho is grateful to the International Olive Council (IOOC) for a doctoral fellowship awarded. J.
392 Moral received a Marie Skłodowska Curie fellowship launched by the European Union’s H2020
393 (contract number 658579).

394 **Notes**

395 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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399 **Figure Captions**

400 **Figure 1.** Distribution of the concentration of phenolic compounds evaluated in the olive oil of 44
401 cultivars during three consecutive crop seasons represented as histogram charts. **AOleAgly** –
402 aldehydic open form of oleuropein aglycone; **MAOleAgly** – monoaldehydic closed form of
403 oleuropein aglycone. **ALigAgly** – aldehydic open form of ligstroside aglycone; **MALigAgly** –
404 monoaldehydic closed form of ligstroside aglycone.
405

406 **Figure 2.** Representation of the variance explained by cultivar (genotype) and noncultivar factors
407 (i.e., crop season, crop season × cultivar, and error) for each phenolic compound. The bubble size
408 explains the relative concentration of each phenol in the evaluated VOOs.
409

410 **Figure 3.** PCA showing the distribution of the cultivars based on the phenolic concentrations in
411 VOOs obtained in three consecutive crop seasons. G-1, cultivars rich in aldehydic forms of oleuropein
412 and ligstroside aglycone; G-2, cultivars rich in oleocantal and oleacein compounds; and G-3,
413 cultivars with no remarkable content of any specific phenolic compound.

414 **Figure 4.** Concentration of the aglycone forms (mg/kg, left) and oleocantal+oleacein (mg/kg, right)
415 in olive oils from different cultivars, which were grouped according their phenolic profile: G-1 (19
416 cultivars), G-2 (13 cultivars), and G-3 (12 cultivars). Columns show the mean concentration, and bars
417 represent the standard error. Significant differences according to the Bonferroni post hoc test were
418 observed among the three groups for both variables.

419 **Supplementary Figure Captions:**

420 **Supplementary Figure 1. A-** Accumulated precipitation (mm) and mean temperature (degrees
421 Celsius) in the three crop seasons. **B-** mean concentration of 'Sum of phenols' in VOOs obtained in
422 the three consecutively evaluated crop seasons.

423 **Supplementary Figure 2.** Linear discriminant analysis (F1: 74.73% and F2: 25.27%): 2D plot
424 showing the discrimination of 264 VOO samples according to the predefined PCA groups (G1, G2,
425 and G3).
426

427 **Table Captions**

428 **Table 1.** Average concentration of phenolic compounds (expressed as mg/kg) for the 44 monovarietal
429 VOOs during the three evaluated crop seasons. Letters indicate the homogeneous groups according
430 to Friedman nonparametric two-way analysis of variance ($P < 0.05$).

431 **Table 2.** Statistical summary by analysis of the phenolic concentration (expressed as mg/kg) in VOOs
432 from 44 cultivars during three consecutive crop seasons.

433 **Table 3.** ANOVA that notes the proportion of variance in phenolic content explained by each factor:
434 cultivar, interannual variability and the resulting interaction.
435
436

437 **Supplementary Table Captions:**

438 **Supplementary Table 1.** Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) parameters for quantitative analysis
439 of phenolic compounds by LC–MS/MS.

440 **Supplementary Table 2.** Olive cultivars classified into the three groups defined by the phenolic
441 profile of VOOs.

442 **Supplementary Table 3.** Discriminant analysis error matrix: total sample reclassification summary.
443 The “% correct” variable indicates the number of olive samples that have been consistently classified
444 over the total number of observations into the same PCA group of G1, G2 or G3.

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640 **Table 1.** Average concentration of phenolic compounds (expressed as mg/kg) for the 44 monovarietal VOOs during the three evaluated crop seasons.
 641 The letters indicate the homogeneous groups according to Friedman nonparametric two-way analysis of variance ($P < 0.05$). Letters indicate significant
 642 differences according to the Friedman test.

Cultivar	Hydroxytyrosol	Apigenin	Luteolin	Oleocanthal	Oleacein	MALigAgly	ALigAgly	MAOleAgly	AOleAgly	Sum of phenols
‘Abou Choki’	1.6 a-d	3.2 a-f	8.0 a-e	189 a-g	252 b-f	122 a-e	396 a-d	305 a-h	262 a-g	1538 a-g
‘Alameño de Montilla’	1.5 a-d	3.3 a-f	9.3 a-e	339 a-g	589 a-f	46.3 a-g	51.9 b-h	108 a-h	75.4 c-g	1224 a-g
‘Alfajara’	1.5 a-d	3.7 a-f	5.9 a-e	852 ab	632 a-f	151 a-c	333 a-e	170 a-h	162 a-g	2311 a-e
‘Arbequina’	0.8 d	5.4 a-f	12.2 a-e	308 a-g	650 a-e	15.1 g	10.5 gh	80.7 d-h	65.6 e-g	1148 a-g
‘Arbosana’	0.9 b-d	15.4 ab	8.8 a-e	190 a-g	256 a-f	13.9 g	12.0 h	37.1 h	48.6 g	583 fg
‘Blanqueta’	2.3 a-d	10.0 a-f	9.9 a-e	477 a-g	606 a-e	27.8 d-g	55.1 d-h	157 a-h	104 a-g	1450 a-g
‘Caballo’	1.4 a-d	2.8 a-f	7.3 a-e	465 a-g	774 a-f	64.6 a-g	83.6 a-h	291 a-h	166 a-g	1856 a-g
‘Cerezuela’	1.7 a-d	2.6 b-f	14.1 a-e	694 a-e	1333 a	90.3 a-g	261 a-h	442 a-f	370 a-e	3208 a
‘Chetoui’	2.8 a-c	5.3 a-f	12.2 a-e	122 a-g	357 a-f	108 a-g	344 a-e	612 a	558 a	2122 a-f
‘Coratina’	2.0 a-d	6.1 a-f	8.8 a-e	300 a-g	427 a-f	130 a-f	486 a-d	512 ab	553 ab	2425 a-d
‘Cornicabra’	1.8 a-d	1.0 ef	3.7 de	412 a-g	645 a-f	224 a	701 a	452 a-d	481 a-c	2923 ab
‘Empeltre’	1.8 a-d	1.6 d-f	7.2 a-e	143 b-g	277 a-f	84.1 a-g	228 a-h	330 a-f	368 a-e	1441 a-g
‘Farga’	1.5 a-d	4.0 a-f	6.6 a-e	183 a-g	339 a-f	62.6 a-g	161 a-h	162 a-h	185 a-g	1106 a-g
‘Frantoio’	2.1 a-d	2.7 b-f	6.3 a-e	218 a-g	261 b-f	233 ab	568 a-c	317 a-h	336 a-f	1944 a-g
‘Gemlik’	1.7 a-d	7.8 a-f	10.8 a-e	97.6 d-g	165 c-f	94.0 a-g	261 a-h	247 a-h	233 a-g	1119 a-g
‘Gordal de Granada’	1.1 a-d	3.7 a-f	9.0 a-e	186 a-g	160 b-f	39.1b-g	50.7 c-h	58.3 f-h	71.3 d-g	579 e-g
‘Hojiblanca’	1.7 a-d	9.7 a-c	20.7 ab	224 a-g	189 a-f	46.3 a-g	48.9 b-h	151 a-h	120 a-g	812 c-g
‘Jabaluna’	1.1 a-d	2.0 c-f	5.5 a-e	298 b-g	124 c-f	39.2b-g	84.6 b-h	140 a-h	102 a-g	795 b-g
‘Kalamon’	2.1 a-d	2.6 b-f	7.2 a-e	1186 a	875 a-c	108 a-g	124 a-h	105 a-h	104 a-g	2514 a-c
‘Koroneiki’	2.1 a-d	5.3 a-f	10.5 a-e	358 a-g	541 a-f	107 a-g	297 a-f	405 a-g	405 a-g	2132 a-g
‘Kotruvsi’	1.1 a-d	15.4 a-c	17.1 a-e	558 a-f	533 a-f	81.0 a-g	120 a-h	131 a-h	115 a-g	1572 a-g
‘Kusha’	2.2 a-d	8.4 a-d	23.4 a	21.9 g	105 f	86.7 a-g	245 a-h	345 a-e	306 a-g	1145 a-g

Cultivar	Hydroxytyrosol	Apigenin	Luteolin	Oleocanthal	Oleacein	MA LigAgly	ALigAgly	MA OleAgly	AOleAgly	Sum of phenols
‘Lechín de Sevilla’	2.6 a-d	1.1 f	1.7 e	94.1 fg	165 b-f	117 a-g	359 a-h	279 a-h	288 a-g	1309 a-g
‘Loaime’	0.8 cd	4.6 a-f	7.4 a-e	405 a-g	215 a-f	42.2b-g	33.6 e-h	56.8 gh	43.1 fg	808 b-g
‘Manzanilla Cazareña’	0.9 a-d	5.1 a-f	8.1 a-e	102 d-g	94.0 c-f	56.2 a-g	98.0 a-h	72.6 c-h	84.8 c-g	522 fg
‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’	5.5 a	2.8 a-f	2.5 de	274 a-g	184 a-f	99.3 a-g	309 a-h	229 a-h	251 a-g	1357 a-g
‘Manzanilla Prieta’	3.7 a-d	2.3 b-f	5.3 b-e	225 a-g	320 a-f	208 a	545 ab	472 a-c	391 a-c	2173 a-f
‘Mastoidis’	2.3 a-d	10.2 a-c	17.0 a-d	190 a-g	149 b-f	131 a-f	274 a-h	207 a-h	227 a-g	1208 a-g
‘Mision Moojeski’	3.3 a-d	19.8 a	17.3 a-c	730 a-c	904 a-d	160 a-d	327 a-h	188 a-h	189 a-g	2538 a-d
‘Mixani’	1.6 a-d	6.6 a-e	21.0 ab	80.1 fg	259 b-f	53.1 a-g	124 a-h	305 a-h	352 a-g	1203 a-g
‘Mollar de Cieza’	1.6 a-d	3.5 a-f	6.7 a-e	232 a-g	250 a-f	22.6 fg	21.3 e-h	77.4 d-h	64.3 e-g	680 fg
‘Morona’	1.5 a-d	9.5 a-c	16.0 a-d	155 a-g	206 b-f	42.6 a-g	52.1 b-h	134 a-h	106 a-g	723 d-g
‘Negrillo de la Carlota’	1.5 a-d	4.3 a-f	15.5 a-d	614 a-d	774 a-d	93.3 a-g	86.9 a-h	158 a-h	86.8 a-g	1835 a-g
‘Ojo de Liebre’	0.8 d	2.7 a-f	9.1 a-e	311 a-g	411 a-f	105 a-g	285 a-h	246 a-h	195 a-g	1566 a-g
‘Pendolino’	0.9 b-d	3.6 a-f	5.7 a-e	580 a-f	616 a-f	93.9 a-g	169 a-h	225 a-h	211 a-g	1906 a-g
‘Picual’	3.5 a-d	2.4 b-f	6.2 a-e	67.1 g	97.3 d-f	84.5 a-g	201 a-h	190 a-h	179 a-g	831 b-g
‘Picual de Almería’	1.9 a-d	1.7 d-f	4.4 b-e	92.5 c-g	188 b-f	111 a-g	279 a-h	344 a-e	379 a-d	1401 a-g
‘Picudo’	2.9 ab	10.7 a-c	16.8 a-d	370 a-g	589 a-f	40.0 b-g	31.9 d-h	126 a-h	67.2 d-g	1255 a-g
‘Plementa Bjelica’	1.2 a-d	11.8 ab	15.3 a-d	936 ab	828 ab	94.6 a-g	268 a-h	328 a-h	358 a-g	2841 ab
‘Royal de Cazorla’	1.2 a-d	4.9 a-f	4.5 c-e	29.7 g	103 ef	14.7 g	16.7 f-h	62.8 e-h	52.5 g	290 g
‘Sabatera’	1.9 a-d	4.7 a-f	9.6 a-e	208 a-g	411 a-f	108 a-g	249 a-h	283 a-h	241 a-g	1515 a-g
‘Sikitita’	1.6 a-d	7.1 a-f	14.9 a-d	233 a-g	262 a-f	22.1 e-g	42.6 d-h	76.3 c-h	88.4 b-g	748 d-g
‘Ulliri i Bardhe i Tiranes’	1.8 a-d	4.9 a-f	12.6 a-e	204 a-g	483 a-f	36.2 c-g	26.2 e-h	88.2 b-h	141 a-g	998 a-g
‘Villalonga’	3.0 a-d	7.9 a-d	10.4 a-e	68.9 e-g	322 b-f	107 a-g	319 a-g	396 a-c	370 a-d	1603 a-g

643 **Table 2.** Statistical summary by analysis of the phenolic concentration (expressed as mg/kg) in VOO from 44 cultivars during three consecutive crop
 644 seasons.

Crop season	Variable	Hydroxytyrosol	Apigenin	Luteolin	Oleocanthal	Oleacein	MALigAgly	ALigAgly	MAOleAgly	AOleAgly	Sum of phenols
2015-2016	Minimum	0.50	0.52	0.54	15.8	12.8	4.4	4.1	39.7	9.9	110
	Maximum	8.2	13.1	13.1	1474	870	157	368	834	903	3139
	Mean	2.3	3.0	3.8	417	276	44.2	80.9	292	242	1360
	SD*	1.7	2.5	2.8	393	219	35.4	76.6	221	216	799
2016-2017	Minimum	0.24	1.1	1.4	1.2	17.9	16.7	8.8	5.8	13.1	324
	Maximum	1.6	25.6	31.7	1441	598	287	778	363	380	2959
	Mean	0.73	8.2	11.2	356	225	110	292	147	218	1370
	SD	0.34	5.7	6.5	286	154	65.1	223	109	87.8	567
2017-2018	Minimum	0.91	0.41	2.3	8.3	48.7	12.9	10.8	49.9	19.6	260
	Maximum	7.5	28.1	38.5	763	2575	380	1048	707	726	4497
	Mean	2.7	6.1	15.9	184	721	106	242	249	192	1719
	SD	1.4	6.4	9.3	165	559	78.1	257	155	181	1030
Average of three crop seasons	Minimum	0.55	0.69	1.4	8.4	26.5	11.4	7.9	31.8	14.2	231
	Maximum	5.7	22.3	27.8	1226	1347	275	731	635	670	3532
	Mean	1.9	5.8	10.3	319	407	86.7	205	230	217	1483
	SD	1.1	4.9	6.2	281	311	59.5	186	162	162	799

* SD: Standard deviation.

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650 **Table 3. ANOVA analysis that points out the proportion of variance in phenolic content explained by each factor: cultivar, interannual**
 651 **variability and the resulting interaction.**
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Factors		Hydroxytyrosol	Apigenin	Luteolin	Oleocanthal	Oleacein	MALigAgly	ALigAgly	MAOleAgly	AOleAgly	Phenolic Sum
Cultivar	$\eta^2(\%)$	30.78	47.43	33.75	61.94	40.76	56.00	54.68	56.21	64.50	66.79
	<i>F</i>	6.76	10.02	9.51	25.92	43.48	38.15	38.7	20.44	36.45	39.8
	<i>p</i>	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Interannual	$\eta^2(\%)$	25.19	11.02	29.51	9.70	27.18	16.24	14.99	11.11	1.62	3.67
	<i>F</i>	118.9	50.06	178.75	87.24	623.35	237.85	228.08	86.87	19.72	47.09
	<i>p</i>	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Cultivar x Interannual	$\eta^2(\%)$	30.05	27.02	25.84	21.01	29.22	23.26	25.96	24.24	28.45	24.44
	<i>F</i>	3.3	2.85	3.64	4.4	15.59	7.92	9.19	4.41	8.04	7.28
	<i>p</i>	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Error	$\eta^2(\%)$	13.98	14.53	10.90	7.34	2.88	4.51	4.34	8.44	5.43	5.15

Eta squared (η^2): percentage of phenolic variability explained by each factor and the interaction.

F ratio: variation between samples/variation within the samples.

p-value: significance level.

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Figure 1. Distribution of the concentration of phenolic compounds evaluated in the olive oil of 44 cultivars during three consecutive crop seasons represented as histograms charts. **AOleAgly** – Aldehydic open form of oleuropein aglycone; **MAOleAgly** – Monoaldehydic closed form of oleuropein aglycone. **ALigAgly** – Aldehydic open form of ligstroside aglycone; **MALigAgly** – Monoaldehydic closed form of ligstroside aglycone.

Figure 2. Representation of the variance explained by cultivar (genotype) and non-cultivar factors (i.e., crop season, crop season \times cultivar, and error) for each phenolic compound. The bubble size explains the relative concentration of each phenol in the evaluated VOOs.

Figure 3. PCA analysis showing the distribution of the cultivars based on the phenolic concentration analyzed in VOO obtained in three consecutive crop seasons. G-1, cultivars rich in aldehydic forms of oleuropein and ligstroside aglycone, G-2, cultivars rich in oleocanthal and oleacein compounds; and G-3, cultivars with not remarkable content in any specific phenolic compound.

Figure 4. Concentration of the aglycone forms (mg/kg, left) and oleocantal+oleacein (mg/kg, right) in olive oils from different cultivars, which were grouped according to their phenolic profile: G-1 (19 cultivars), G-2 (13 cultivars), and G-3 (12 cultivars). Columns shows the mean concentration and bars represent the standard error. Significant differences according to Bonferroni post-host test were observed among the three groups for both variables.

Supplementary Table 1. Multiple Reaction Monitoring (MRM) parameters for quantitative analysis of phenolic compounds by LC–MS/MS.

Phenolic compounds	Retention time (min)	Q1 voltage (V)	Precursor ion (<i>m/z</i>)	Collision energy (eV)	Quantitative transition (<i>m/z</i>)	Product ion confirmation (<i>m/z</i>)	
Hydroxytyrosol	2.1	110	153.1	10	153-123	108	
3,4-DHPEA-EDA (Oleacein)	4.3	110	319.1	12	319-59	139	
3,4-DHPEA-EA	AOleAgly	4.6	110	377	12	377-275	307
	MAOleAgly	5.9	110	377	12	377-275	307
p-HPEA-EDA (Oleocanthal)	5.4	110	303.1	12	303-59	137	
p-HPEA-EA	ALigAgly	5.5	110	361.1	12	361-291	101
	MALigAgly	6.2	110	361.1	12	361-291	101
Luteolin	6.3	170	285	35	285-133	175	
Apigenin	6.6	170	269	35	269-117	151	

AOleAgly – Aldehydic open form of oleuropein aglycone; **MAOleAgly** – Monoaldehydic closed form of oleuropein aglycone.
ALigAgly – Aldehydic open form of ligstroside aglycone; **MALigAgly** – Monoaldehydic closed form of ligstroside aglycone.

Supplementary Table 2. Olive cultivars classified into the three groups defined by the phenolic profile of VOO.

“G-1” ●	“G-2” ●	“G-3” ●
Abou Choki	Alameño de Montilla	Arbosana
Chetoui	Alfajara	Farga
Coratina	Arbequina	Gordal de Granada
Cornicabra	Blanqueta	Hojiblanca
Empeltre	Caballo	Jabaluna
Frantoio	Cerezuela	Loaime
Gemlik	Kalamon	Manzanilla Cazareña
Koroneiki	Kotruvsi	Mollar de Cieza
Kusha	Mision Moojeski	Morona
Lechín de Sevilla	Negrillo de la Carlota	Royal de Cazorla
Manzanilla de Sevilla	Pendolino	Sikitita
Manzanilla Prieta	Picudo	Ulliri i Bardhe i Tiranes
Mastoidis	Plementa Bjelica	
Mixani		
Ojo de Liebre		
Picual		
Picual de Almería		
Sabatera		
Villalonga		

G-1: rich in aldehydic form of oleuropein and ligstroside aglycone, **G-2** rich in oleocanthal and oleacein, and **G-3** balanced and no remarkable cultivars to any specific phenolic profile.

Supplementary Table 3. Discriminant Analysis error matrix: total samples reclassification summary. The “% correct” variable indicates the number of olive samples that have been consistently classified over the total number of observations into the same PCA group G1, G2 and G3.

From ↓ \ To →		DA reclassification ²			Total	% correct
		G1	G2	G3		
PCA classification ¹	G1	99	0	15	114	86.84%
	G2	2	58	12	72	80.56%
	G3	4	6	68	78	87.18%
Total		105	64	95	264	85.23%

¹Cultivars classification (clustering) using the mean phenolic concentration.

²Cultivars reclassification using the total observations (samples replication).

Supplementary Fig. 1. A- Accumulated precipitations (mm) and mean temperature (Celsius degrees) in the three crop seasons. B- Mean concentration of 'Sum of phenols' in the VOOs obtained in the three consecutively evaluated crop seasons.

Supplementary Figure 2. Linear Discriminant Analysis (F1: 74.73%, and F2: 25.27%): 2D plot showing the discrimination of 264 VOO samples according to the predefined PCA groups (G1, G2, and G3).